

4-Quinazolones : Part VI. Synthesis of an Angular Furoquinazolone

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The synthesis of 2,2'-dimethyl-7-methoxy-3-phenylfuro(4',5' : 5,6)quinazolin-4(3H)-one (XV) is described.

In a previous communication¹ of this series we described the synthesis of some angular furoquinazolones in which the furan ring was fused at the 7,8-positions of a quinazolone moiety. We now report the synthesis of an angular furoquinazolone wherein the furan ring is built at the alternative 5,6-positions of the quinazolone ring. Based on the synthetic sequences adopted earlier¹, the synthesis of 2,2'-dimethyl-7-methoxy-3-phenylfuro(4',5' : 5,6)quinazolin-4(3H)-one (XV) has been accomplished. The intermediate 6-hydroxy-7-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VII) required for building the furan ring was secured as follows. Nitration of veratric acid followed by selective demethylation of the resulting 6-nitroveratric acid with boiling aqueous potassium hydroxide furnished 3-hydroxy-4-methoxy-6-nitrobenzoic acid (I). Earlier workers² prepared it by alkaline hydrolysis of methyl 6-nitroveratrate which was obtained by nitration of methyl veratrate. Reduction of I with sodium dithionite yielded 3-hydroxy-4-methoxy-6-aminobenzoic acid (II) which was transformed into 6-acetoxy-7-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VI) by *two routes*. Acetylation of II gave 3-acetoxy-4-methoxy-6-acetamidobenzoic acid (III) which, on interaction with aniline in boiling toluene in the presence of phosphorus trichloride, was converted into the quinazolone (VI). Alternatively, II when refluxed with acetic anhydride afforded 6-acetoxy-7-methoxy-2-methyl-4H,3,1-benzoxazine-4-one (IV) which, unlike other 2-methyl benzoxazines is stable, can be preserved without undergoing deterioration and remains unchanged even when kept in contact with water at room temperature. IV did not give the expected quinazolone (VI) when treated with aniline in boiling

- I : R = NO₂; R₁ = COOH; R₂ = H
 II : R = NH₂; R₁ = COOH; R₂ = H
 III : R = NHCOCH₃; R₁ = COOH; R₂ = H
 V : R = NHCOCH₃; R₁ = CONHPh; R₂ = COCH₃

1. Part III. S. K. P. Sinha and D. N. Chaudhury, *This Journal*, 1968, in press.
 2. M. Greenwood and R. Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 1371.

toluene but yielded the bisamide (V) which, however, was cyclised to (VI) with boiling acetic anhydride. Subsequent deacetylation with sodium methoxide furnished the desired intermediate quinazolone (VII).

Treatment with allyl bromide in DMF in the presence of potassium carbonate converted VII into 6-allyloxy-7-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VIII) which, on Claisen rearrangement in boiling diethylaniline, afforded 5-allyl-6-hydroxy-7-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (IX). While methylation with diazomethane gave 5-allyl-6,7-dimethoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (X), acetylation with acetic anhydride in pyridine produced 5-allyl-6-acetoxy-7-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XI). Interaction of XI with pyridinium bromide perbromide in glacial acetic

VI : R = H; R₁ = COCH₃

VII : R = R₁ = H

VIII : R = H; R₁ = allyl

IX : R = allyl; R₁ = H

X : R = allyl; R₁ = CH₃

XI : R = allyl; R₁ = COCH₃

XII : R = CH₂-CHBr-CH₂Br; R₁ = COCH₃

XIII : R = CH₂-CHBr-CH₂Br; R₁ = H

XIV : R = CH₂-CHBr-CH₃; R₁ = H

acid yielded 6-acetoxy-5-(2',3'-dibromopropyl)-7-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XII), identical with the specimen obtained by the action of pyridinium bromide perbromide on the hydroxy quinazolone (IX) followed by acetylation of the resulting 6-hydroxy-5-(2',3'-dibromopropyl)-7-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XIII). Both XII and XIII were cyclised to 2,2'-dimethyl-7-methoxy-3-phenylfuro(4',5':5,6)quinazolin-4(3H)-one (XV) by the action of hot alcoholic potassium hydroxide. The furoquinazolone (XV) was also synthesised by an *alternative route* which involved the preparation of the

XV

XVI

dihydrofuroquinazolone (XVI) according to the method of Claisen³ and its subsequent dehydrogenation. On heating IX with 48% hydrobromic acid for 15 min. an alkali soluble bromine containing solid, believed to be 6-hydroxy-5-(2'-bromopropyl)-7-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XIV), separated out as the major product; from the residual

solution a small amount of the cyclised product, 2',3'-dihydro-2,2'-dimethyl-7-methoxy-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XVI), was isolated. The formulation of the bromo compound (XIV) was deduced from its elemental analysis and from the fact that it could be cyclised to the dihydrofuroquinazolone (XVI) by the action of hot alcoholic potassium hydroxide. XVI was, however, obtained as the sole product from IX when the period of heating with hydrobromic acid was extended to 4 hrs. Subsequent dehydrogenation of XVI with palladised charcoal furnished the furoquinazolone (XV).

EXPERIMENTAL

All m.ps and b.ps are uncorrected. Organic extracts were dried with Na_2SO_4 . Light petroleum used had b.p. 60–80°.

6-Nitroveratric acid: It has been prepared earlier⁴ from veratraldehyde by nitration followed by oxidation. It is now obtained from veratric acid by direct nitration as follows: Veratric acid (18.2 g.; 0.01 mole) was added portionwise with stirring during 1 hr. to conc. HNO_3 (100 ml. d, 1.42) at 0–5°. After the addition was over, the reaction mixture was stirred for a further period of 0.5 hr., the temperature being not allowed to rise above 10°. It was poured into crushed ice, vigorously agitated and the yellow solid that separated was filtered and washed thoroughly with water. Crystallisations from EtOH furnished 6-nitroveratric acid as yellow needles (18 g.; 80%), m.p. 190–191° (lit.⁴ m.p. 191–192°).

3-Hydroxy-4-methoxy-6-nitrobenzoic acid (I): 6-Nitroveratric acid (11.35 g.; 0.05 mole) was refluxed with 20% aq. KOH (75 ml.) for 12 hr. The homogeneous solution was filtered from traces of impurities, cooled and acidified with conc. HCl to afford K-salt of I as yellow needles (12 g.; 90%), m.p. 285° (dec.). Further addition of conc. HCl ($\text{pH} = 2$) to this mixture or acidification of an aq. solution of the K-salt gave yellow rectangular prisms of I (9.1 g.; 85%), m.p. 181–182° (lit.⁴ m.p. 181°).

3-Hydroxy-4-methoxy-6-aminobenzoic acid (II): A solution of the K-salt of I (2.89 g.; 0.01 mole) or of I (2.13 g.; 0.01 mole) in 10% aq. KOH (20 ml.), at 60°, was treated with Na_2SO_4 (7 g.; 0.04 mole) in portions during 0.5 hr. After completion of the addition, the almost colorless solution was kept at 50–60° for 1 hr., filtered from traces of impurities, cooled in ice-bath and acidified ($\text{pH} = 2$) with conc. HCl. The white precipitate that separated out was crystallised from dilute EtOH to give II as colorless needles (1.8 g.; 90%), m.p. 214–215°. (Found: C, 52.2; H, 5.2; N, 7.8. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_9\text{O}_4\text{N}$ requires C, 52.4; H, 4.9; N, 7.6%).

3-Acetoxy-4-methoxy-6-acetamidobenzoic acid (III): A mixture of II (1.83 g.; 0.01 mole) and Ac_2O (10 ml.; 0.1 mole) was refluxed for 1 hr. and then poured into crushed ice when a precipitate was obtained. Next day, it was filtered and crystallised from dilute EtOH to yield III as colorless needles (2.5 g.; 93%), m.p. 203–204°. Several crystallisations from dilute EtOH or ethyl acetate-light petroleum afforded the pure specimen, m.p. 210–211°. (Found: C, 54.1; H, 5.0; N, 5.4. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{13}\text{O}_6\text{N}$ requires C, 53.9; H, 4.8; N, 5.2%).

6-Acetoxy-7-methoxy-2-methyl-4H,3,1-benzoxazine-4-one (IV) : II (1.83 g.; 0.01 mole) or III (2.7 g.; 0.01 mole) was refluxed with Ac_2O (5 ml.; 0.05 mole) for 1 hr. and left overnight. The colorless needles which gradually deposited were collected, washed with dry ether to afford IV (1.2 g.; 50%), m.p. 197–198°. An analytical sample crystallised from glacial AcOH melted at 200–201°. (Found : C, 57.5; H, 4.5; N, 5.5. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_5\text{N}$ requires C, 57.8; H, 4.4; N, 5.6%).

3-Acetoxy-4-methoxy-6-acetamidobenzanilide (V) : IV (2.37 g.; 0.01 mole) was refluxed with PhNH_2 (0.9 ml.; 0.01 mole) in dry toluene (10 ml.) for 4 hr. using a Dean-Stark water separator. The solvent (5 ml.) was distilled off and the solid that separated from the cooled concentrated solution filtered and washed with benzene. Crystallisations from dilute EtOH yielded V as colorless needles (2.3 g.; 70%), m.p. 255–256°. (Found : C, 63.3; H, 5.4; N, 8.2. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_5\text{N}_2$ requires C, 63.1; H, 5.2; N, 8.1%).

The toluene filtrate on treatment with light petroleum, gave a little colorless solid which on crystallisation from EtOH furnished colorless rectangular prisms, m.p. 197–198°, identified as the quinazolone VI (See below).

6-Acetoxy-7-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VI)—Method (a) : A mixture of III (2.67 g.; 0.01 mole), PhNH_2 (0.93 ml.; 0.01 mole) and PCl_3 (0.3 ml.; 0.0035 mole) in toluene (25 ml.) was refluxed for 6 hr. in an oil-bath at 110–120°. On cooling, a solid separated which was filtered and washed with ether. Crystallisations from EtOH gave the hydrochloride of VI as colorless needles, m.p. 192–193°. These were triturated with 10% aq. Na_2CO_3 , filtered, washed with water and crystallised twice from EtOH to give VI as colorless rectangular prisms (2.6 g.; 80%), m.p. 197–198°. (Found : C, 66.7; H, 5.0; N, 8.9. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_4\text{N}_2$ requires C, 66.6; H, 4.9; N, 8.6%).

Method (b) : A mixture of V (3.28 g.; 0.01 mole) and Ac_2O (5 ml.) was refluxed for 1 hr. and poured into crushed ice when a white solid separated. On crystallisation from dilute EtOH, VI was obtained as colorless rectangular prisms (2.9 g.; 90%), m.p. 197–198°, undepressed on admixture with the sample obtained as in (a).

6-Hydroxy-7-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VII) : VI (0.32 g.; 0.001 mole) in dry MeOH (15 ml.) was treated with a solution of Na (0.1 g.), in dry MeOH (10 ml.) and kept overnight. Excess of MeOH (20 ml.) was distilled off, the residual solution diluted with water and chilled to give a crystalline material. It was collected and crystallised from dilute MeOH to afford VII as colorless needles (0.21 g.; 75%), m.p. 260–261°. (Found : C, 67.8; H, 5.1; N, 10.1. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$ requires C, 68.0; H, 4.9; N, 9.9%).

6-Allyloxy-7-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (VIII) : To a solution of VII (2.82 g.; 0.01 mole) in MDF (25 ml.) allyl bromide (0.9 ml.; 0.011 mole) and K_2CO_3 (1.5 g.) were added with vigorous shaking and left overnight. The reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice, the precipitated solid filtered and washed well with water. On crystallisation from dilute EtOH VIII was isolated as colorless needles (3 g.; 92%), m.p. 176–177°. (Found : C, 70.5; H, 5.8; N, 8.4. $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_3\text{N}_2$ requires C, 70.8; H, 5.6; N, 8.7%).

5-Allyl-6-hydroxy-7-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (IX) : VIII suspended in freshly distilled PhNEt_2 (35 ml.) was refluxed for 4 hr. in CO_2 atmosphere in an

oil-bath at 215–22° when almost a dark solution obtained. It was filtered hot from traces of suspended impurities, excess of PhNEt₂ (25 ml.) distilled off, the residual solution diluted with benzene and extracted thoroughly with 10% aq. NaOH. The alkaline extract, on acidification with conc. HCl, gave a precipitate which was filtered and washed well with water. Crystallisation from dilute MeOH afforded IX as colorless needles (9 g.; 90%), m.p. 110–111°. (Found: C, 71.0; H, 5.8; N, 8.9. C₁₉H₁₈O₃N₂ requires C, 70.8; H, 5.6; N, 8.7%).

5-Allyl-6,7-dimethoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(4H)-one (X): IX (0.65 g.; 0.0015 mole) in ether was treated with excess ethereal CH₂N₂ (from 0.45 g. nitrosomethyl urea) and left overnight. The solvent was evaporated and the residue was crystallised from MeOH to yield X as colorless needles (0.53 g.; 80%) m.p. 181–182°. (Found: C, 71.7; H, 6.1; N, 8.0. C₂₀H₂₀O₃N₂ requires C, 71.4; H, 5.9; N, 8.3%).

6-Acetoxy-5-allyl-7-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XI): A solution of IX (4.83 g.; 0.015 mole) in dry pyridine (10 ml.) was treated with Ac₂O (6 ml.) and left overnight. It was poured into crushed ice, the precipitated solid was collected and washed with water. It was crystallised from EtOH to give XI as colorless cubes (4.9 g.; 90%), m.p. 220–221°. (Found: C, 69.0; H, 5.7; N, 7.9. C₂₁H₂₀O₄N₂ requires C, 69.2; H, 5.5; N, 7.7%).

6-Acetoxy-5-(2',3'-dibromopropyl)-7-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XII): A solution of XI (1 g.; 0.00275 mole) in glacial AcOH (5 ml.) was treated with pyridinium bromide perbromide (1 g.; 0.003125 mole) suspended in AcOH (10 ml.) and stirred mechanically at room temperature. After 0.5 hr. the reagent was consumed and a precipitate of colorless dibromide gradually deposited which was filtered, washed successively with AcOH and ice-cold AcOEt. Crystallisation from EtOH afforded XII as colorless needles (1.15 g.; 80%), m.p. 182–183°. (Found: C, 47.9; H, 4.0; N, 5.5; Br, 30.7. C₂₁H₂₀O₄N₂Br₂ requires C, 48.1; H, 3.8; N, 5.3; Br, 30.5%).

6-Hydroxy-5-(2',3'-dibromopropyl)-7-methoxy-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XIII): IX (1.771 g.; 0.0055 mole) in glacial AcOH (10 ml.) was treated with a suspension of pyridinium bromide per bromide (2 g.; 0.00625 mole) in glacial AcOH (10 ml.) and stirred mechanically at the room temperature. After 0.5 hr. the reagent was consumed and the reaction mixture left overnight. It was diluted with water and on being kept in refrigerator colorless solid separated. It was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from EtOH to furnish XIII as colorless needles (1.6 g.; 60%), m.p. 257–258°. (Found: C, 47.1; H, 4.0; N, 5.9; Br, 32.9. C₁₉H₁₈O₃N₂Br₂ requires C, 47.3; H, 3.7; N, 5.8; Br, 33.1%).

Acetylation of XIII in the usual way afforded its acetate XII, m.p. and mixed m.p. 182–183°.

6-Hydroxy-7-methoxy-5-(2'-bromopropyl)-2-methyl-3-phenylquinazolin-4(3H)-one (XIV): IX (0.8 g.; 0.0025 mole) was refluxed with 48% aq. HBr (8 ml.) for 10 min. when a clear solution was obtained. On further heating for an additional period of 5 min. a white solid separated. The reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with water and the solid filtered. Crystallisation from MeOH gave XIV as colorless needles (0.8 g.; 80%), m.p. 265–266°.

(Found : C, 56.9; H, 4.4; N, 7.1; Br, 20.0. $C_{19}H_{19}O_3N_2Br$ requires C, 56.6; H, 4.7; N, 6.9; Br, 19.8%).

The methanolic mother liquor was concentrated and on careful dilution with water deposited colorless silky needles (0.05 g.), m.p. 217–218° undepressed on admixture with the specimen of *dihydrofuroquinazalone* (XVI) (See below).

2',3'-Dihydro-2,2'-dimethyl-7-methoxy-3-phenylfuro[4',5':5,6]quinazolin-4(3H)-one (XVI): (i) IX (1.6 g.; 0.005 mole) was refluxed with 48% aq. HBr (20 ml.) for 10 min. when the compound dissolved but a solid separated out after the heating was continued for an additional period of 5 min. The reaction mixture was further heated for 4 hr. on a steam-bath to avoid bumping and then diluted with water; the solid was filtered off and washed well with water. Crystallisations from dilute MeOH gave XVI as colorless needles (1 g.; 60%), m.p. 217–218°. (Found : C, 70.6; H, 5.8; N, 8.5. $C_{19}H_{18}O_3N_2$ requires C, 70.8; H, 5.6; N, 8.7%).

(ii) XIV (1 g.; 0.0025 mole) was heated with a solution of KOH (0.9 g.; 0.015 mole) in EtOH (20 ml.) on a steam bath for 2 hr., EtOH (15 ml.) distilled off and the residual solution diluted with water. On cooling in ice-bath, silky colorless needles separated which were filtered and washed with water. Crystallisation from dilute MeOH furnished XVI as colorless silky needles (0.6 g.; 75%), m.p. and mixed m.p. 217–217° as in (i).

2,2'-Dimethyl-7-methoxy-3-phenylfuro[4',5' : 5,6]quinazolin-4(3H)-one (XV) : (i) XII (0.8 g.; 0.0015 mole) was refluxed with a solution of KOH (0.9 g.; 0.015 mole) in EtOH (20 ml.) for 2 hr., EtOH (15 ml.) distilled off, the residual solution diluted with water and cooled in ice. The silky colorless needles that separated were filtered, washed with water and dried. Purification by chromatography of its benzene solution over Brockmann's alumina and subsequent recrystallisation from isopropanol or MeOH furnished XV as colorless silky needles (0.6 g.; 75%), m.p. 266–267°. (Found : C, 71.0; H, 5.2; N, 9.0. $C_{19}H_{18}O_3N_2$ requires C, 71.2; H, 5.0; N, 8.7%). IR(KBr) 1630, 1700 cm^{-1} (C=O); UV max (EtOH) 251 $m\mu$ (E, 33926) (Furan).

(ii) XIII (0.7 g.; 0.0015 mole) was refluxed with a solution of KOH (0.9 g.; 0.015 mole) in EtOH (20 ml.) for 2 hr. and worked up as above. The product isolated was crystallised from isopropanol or MeOH to give XV as white silky needles (0.4 g.; 50%), m.p. and mixed m.p. 266–267°.

(iii) A mixture of XVI (0.25 g.), diphenyl ether (10 ml.) and 1% Pd-C (0.1 g.) was refluxed for 10 hr., filtered hot and the filtrate was steam distilled to remove the solvent. The solid residue, on crystallisation from isopropanol, gave XV as colorless silky needles (0.1 g., 40%), m.p. and mixed m.p. 266–267°.